

Editorial

Adopting Nutrition-Based Measures in Managing COVID-19 Pandemic: Perspectives of Medical Practitioners and Nutritionists

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Adopting Nutrition-Based Measures in Managing COVID-19 Pandemic: Perspectives of Medical Practitioners and Nutritionists

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Abstract: Coronavirus disease (also called COVID-19, 2019-nCov or 2019 Novel Coronavirus) is associated with respiration-related symptoms such as cough, fever, pneumonia, and sometimes death. This study examined the comparison in the perceptions of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the relationship between good nutrition and the coronavirus disease. Three research hypotheses were postulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research approach was adopted. Ninety-one medicals and nutritionists were selected in Ondo West Local Government as respondents. A self-developed and validated questionnaire titled "Utilization of Good Dietary Pattern in the Management of COVID-19 Pandemic Questionnaire" was the instrument used for data collection. Data collected were analysed with mean, standard deviation and t-test of significance difference. Findings revealed that both classes of respondents agreed with no significant difference that the possible consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of the populace include a breakdown in the immune system, inflammation of the respiratory tract, multi-organ failure, and mortality ($\bar{x} \geq 2.50$) and that good nutrition can aid in the management of COVID-19 pandemic through immune boosting and increased resistance against infections. Their responses are slightly different regarding the roles of high biological value proteins and lipids in COVID-19 Management as well as about the facts that multi-organ failure upon the advancement of COVID-19 and that COVID-19 complications can be prevented through the exertion of anti-inflammatory effect in the gut. The study concluded that the consumption of a good nutritious diet can aid the management of COVID-19 before and after the infection, as it will boost individuals' immune systems. It was therefore recommended that the consumption of nutrient-dense diets and immune-boosting food should be prioritized in managing COVID-19.

Key Words: COVID-19, disease management, immune boosting, medical practitioners, nutritionists, nutrition

I. INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus disease (also called COVID-19, 2019-nCov or 2019 Novel Coronavirus) is an infectious disease caused by a new strain of coronavirus, which until its discovery was not identified in humans. It is associated with flu-like symptoms such as cough, fever, pneumonia, and sometimes, death. Its novelty has put the members of the scientific community on their heels as effective and sustainable vaccines to mitigate the hydra-headed virus and drugs to treat the pathology are being sourced for. Reducing inflammation and ensuring that patients can give necessary immune responses at the same time was a critical challenge. Facts such as the one reported

by Handu *et al.* (2021) that adults infected with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) showed a significant impact of malnutrition on health outcomes, should inform the search for remedies to the global malady. In other words, scientists needed to explore the potential of foods and much as in drugs. The eventualities of the COVID-19 pandemic have reflected the indispensable need for good and adequate nutrition and dietary habits. They are expedient to minimize the occurrence of Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) and modulate the inflammatory status of infected individuals. From another perspective, the health status of recovered patients can be affected by improper nutrition during infection (Brugliera *et al.*, 2020; Fernández-Quintela *et al.*, 2020; Zabetakis *et al.*, 2020).

Based on the available information on the treatment given to coronavirus disease patients, the nutritional remedy is the first-line treatment. First, nutrition is essential for the survival of man—hale, invalid and convalescent. Further from this, nutrition care is identified as a means of addressing malnutrition to treat and prevent further adverse health outcomes from COVID-19 infection. Since the disease spontaneously overpowers the immune system and unleashes infections in the respiratory system, appropriate intake of a well-balanced diet which constitutes all essential nutrients in the right proportion will be of great help to the immune system. Also, the intake of certain micronutrients in amounts exceeding their recommended dietary allowances is recommended since infections and other stressors can reduce micronutrient status (Fernández-Quintela *et al.*, 2020).

Studies have established the importance of nutrition in the building of the body's immunity to infections. Protein deficiency is said to negatively affect the number of functional immunoglobulins and gut-associated lymphoid tissue, thus impairing the immune system function. The quality and quantity of proteins consumed are also important here. Therefore, high biological value proteins (such as those present in eggs, lean meat, fish, and dairy) which contain all the essential amino acids and can exert anti-inflammatory effects in the body should be included in the diets of COVID-19 patients. Also, amino acids like arginine and glutamine can positively influence the immune system (Iddir *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, omega-3 fatty acids – docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) – can render enveloped viruses inactive and prevent viral replication. These two essential fatty acids (DHA and EPA) suppress the production of prostaglandin which could cause inflammation, by inhibiting the activity of cyclooxygenase enzymes (COX) (Zabetakis *et al.*, 2020). They can lower the rate of Platelet-Activating Factors (PAF) biosynthesis, as

well as increase the rate of those involved in its degradation. Also, Platelet activation may be blocked as a way of preventing thrombosis (the blockage of blood vessels by blood clots) associated with COVID-19 (Lordan *et al.*, 2021; Zabetakis *et al.*, 2020).

Carbohydrates and dietary fibres are not left out in this all-important role of nutrition in COVID-19 management. The consumption of highly processed carbohydrates which have higher glycemic indexes can overload the mitochondrion and lead to the synthesis of free radicals. On the other hand, the consumption of highly caloric foods can help reduce inflammation, while sufficient fibre consumption (about 25–35 g/day) can facilitate correct metabolic functioning and reduce both gut and systemic inflammation (particularly, by lowering the number of inflammatory cytokines such as CRP, TNF- α and IL-6) (Iddir *et al.*, 2020). Vitamins A, C, D, E, B₆ and B₁₂ minerals (such as folate, iron, and magnesium) and trace elements like zinc, selenium and copper help reduce disease susceptibility (Maggini *et al.*, 2008, 2018) and the maintenance of immune function (Calder, 2013). Deficiencies in these nutrients negatively affect the immune system, resulting in decreased resistance against infections. Vitamins and minerals are essential for adaptive immunity as they are involved in cytokine production, lymphocyte differentiation and proliferation, antibody production, and generation of memory cells.

This study, therefore, seeks to study the comparison in the perceptions of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the relationship between good nutrition and the coronavirus disease.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Good nutrition has been identified as one of the most effective approaches to addressing the effects of COVID-19 on human physical and mental health. However, there remains an observable gulf in the coherence of facts held by medical practitioners and nutritionists in this regard. This may be because the first class of people handle nutrition as only a supplement to remedies or cures expected to be supplied by pharmaceutical products, while the latter group believe strongly in the cogency of nutrition in treating, or in a more ideal sense, preventing or protecting against ailments including such ones as the dreaded COVID-19. Meanwhile, these disparities will only continue to threaten the credibility ascribed to the information supplied by the two groups of professionals. It becomes therefore necessary to compare (and if necessary, contrast) the perspectives of the duo on the role of good nutrition in the management of the COVID-19 pandemic. Also, there is a need to create more awareness among the populace of the importance of good and immune-boosting nutrition in combating COVID-19.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to juxtapose the perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists about the adoption of nutrition-based measures in managing the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, the study documented the comparative perceptions of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the:

1. consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of the populace,
2. general roles of good nutrition in the management of the

- COVID-19 pandemic, and
3. specific nutrition-based measures in the management of the COVID-19 Pandemic.

IV. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses shall be tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: The perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of the populace are not significantly different.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the general role of good nutrition in the management of the COVID-19 pandemic.

H₀₃: The perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the specific nutrition-based measures in the management of the COVID-19 Pandemic are not significantly different.

V. METHODOLOGY

The design used for this study was the descriptive survey design as it allows for the examination of the interaction between the variables under study (profession, nutrition and coronavirus disease) and the implications of the findings. The population of the study consisted of Health Workers and Nutritionists in Ondo State. The simple random sampling technique was used to select a total of ninety-one (91) respondents: forty-six (46) males and forty-five (45) females.

A self-structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. It consisted of five sections: 'A' to 'E'. Section A was meant to elicit information on the personal data of the respondents while Sections B, C, D and E contained question items intended to obtain information to answer the four research questions raised for the study. The questionnaire was constructed on a four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The research instrument for the study was validated by three experts in the Department of Home Economics, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. Their observations, suggestions and comments were used to make constructive corrections in the final copy of the instrument. Copies of the questionnaire were administered electronically to elites (using Google form) and in person to other respondents.

The data collected was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test. The decision rule was that any mean value equal to or greater than 2.50 is regarded as agreed, while any mean value below 2.50 is considered as disagreed. Further, when the 2-tailed significant value at 0.05 level of significance is less than 0.05, the difference in the mean responses of the two categories of respondents is taken to be significant. Else, the difference is said not to be statistically significant. This is done for every single item under each hypothesis and for the summation of the responses needed to test each hypothesis.

VI. RESULTS

Research Hypothesis 1: The perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of the populace are not significantly different.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and T-test Analysis of the Perspective of Medical Practitioners and Nutritionists on the Consequences of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Health of the Populace

nM = 57; nN = 34; df = 89; COP = 2.50; $\rho = 0.05$							
S/N	ITEMS	Respondents	\bar{x}	SD	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
1.	Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) may cause interstitial pneumonia and respiratory distress syndrome, which can lead to multi-organ failure.	Medicals	3.60	0.495	-1.644	0.104	NS
		Nutritionists	3.76	0.431			
2.	COVID-19 can lead to break down of the immune system of the body	Medicals	3.84	0.492	0.909	0.366	NS
		Nutritionists	3.74	0.618			
3.	COVID-19 can cause acute inflammation of the respiratory tract	Medicals	3.91	0.285	1.966	0.052	NS
		Nutritionists	3.76	0.431			
4.	Multi-organ failure occurs as the disease advances	Medicals	3.89	0.310	3.378	0.001	S
		Nutritionists	3.59	0.557			
5.	Lung capacity is reduced by damage to pulmonary tissues	Medicals	3.67	0.852	0.752	0.454	NS
		Nutritionists	3.53	0.825			
6.	COVID-19 leads to the stigmatization of patients which in turn affect their psychological health	Medicals	3.16	0.922	-1.206	0.231	NS
		Nutritionists	3.38	0.739			
7.	Complications can result from damage to the blood vessels	Medicals	3.65	0.612	1.305	0.195	NS
		Nutritionists	3.47	0.662			
8.	The pandemic can lead to mortality.	Medicals	3.79	0.559	-0.300	0.765	NS
		Nutritionists	3.82	0.459			
	Grand	Medicals	29.51	2.361	0.802	0.425	NS
		Nutritionists	29.06	2.933			

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Keys: nM = Number of Medical Practitioners
df = Degree of Freedom
 ρ = Level of Significance
SD = Standard Deviation
S = Significant

nN = Number of Nutritionists
COP = Cut-Off-Point
 \bar{x} = Mean Value of Responses
NS = Not Significant
t = Calculated t-value

Table 1 shows the mean responses of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the possible consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of the populace. The means of the responses range from 3.16 to 3.91 which is greater than the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicates that both sets of respondents agreed that COVID-19 can lead to acute inflammation of the respiratory tract, breakdown of the immune system, mortality, multi-organ failure upon the advancement of the disease, pulmonary tissue damage, interstitial pneumonia and respiratory distress syndrome, damage in the blood vessels, and stigmatization of patients. The standard deviations of the responses ranged from 0.310 to 0.922 indicating that the responses clustered around the mean. However, the t-test analysis revealed that the responses of the

medical practitioners and nutritionists are not significantly different on the foregoing points, except for the point that multi-organ failure upon the advancement of COVID-19. The medicals gave a mean response that is much higher than that of the nutritionists on the point. Summarily, there is no significant difference between the perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of the populace.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the general role of good nutrition in the management of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation and T-test Analysis of the Perspective of Medical Practitioners and Nutritionists on the General Role of Good Nutrition in the Management of the COVID-19 Pandemic

nM = 57; nN = 34; df = 89; COP = 2.50; $\rho = 0.05$							
S/N	ITEMS	Respondents	\bar{x}	SD	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
1.	Immune boosting, which is an important step in fighting against COVID-19 infection	Medicals	3.88	0.327	-0.365	0.716	NS
		Nutritionists	3.84	0.591			
2.	Exertion of anti-inflammatory effects in the gut helps prevent COVID-19 complications.	Medicals	3.88	0.327	-3.264	0.002	S
		Nutritionists	2.84	0.978			
3.	An increase in resistance to infections such as COVID-19 can be achieved through a good diet	Medicals	3.53	0.961	-1.634	0.106	NS
		Nutritionists	3.51	0.928			
4.	Control of metabolic functions to prevent multi-organ dysfunction	Medicals	3.79	0.538	-1.472	0.145	NS
		Nutritionists	3.33	1.006			
5.	Prevention of damage to the blood vessels that commonly exist in COVID-19 patients	Medicals	3.62	0.652	-0.996	0.322	NS
		Nutritionists	3.51	0.848			
	Grand	Medicals	17.04	2.927	-2.528	0.013	S
		Nutritionists	18.50	2.178			

Source: Field Survey (2021)

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nN = Number of Nutritionists
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 \bar{x} = Mean Value of Responses
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Table 2 shows the mean responses of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the general role of good nutrition in the management of the COVID-19 pandemic. The mean values of the responses range from 2.84 to 3.88 which are greater than the cut-off point of 2.50. This means both sets of respondents agreed that the general role of good nutrition in COVID-19 management includes immune boosting, increase in resistance against infections, prevention of damage to the blood vessels, control of metabolic functions and exertion of anti-inflammatory effect in the gut as to prevent COVID-19 complications. The standard deviations of the responses ranged from 0.538 to 1.006 indicating that the responses are slightly scattered around the mean. However, the t-test analysis revealed that the responses of the medical

practitioners and nutritionists are not significantly different on the foregoing points, except for the point that exerting anti-inflammatory effect in the gut to prevent COVID-19 complications, where the responses of the medicals deviate very highly from the mean value, unlike those of the nutritionists. On a cumulative ground, there is a significant difference between the perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the general role of good nutrition in the management of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Hypothesis 3: The perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the specific nutrition-based measures in the management of the COVID-19 Pandemic are not significantly different.

Table 3: T-test Analysis of the Perspective of Medical Practitioners and Nutritionists on the Specific Nutrition-Based Measures in the Management of the COVID-19 Pandemic

nM = 57; nN = 34; df = 89; COP = 2.50; $\rho = 0.05$																																																																						
S/N	ITEMS	Respondents	\bar{x}	SD	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision																																																															
1.	High biological value proteins (in lean meat, fish and dairy products) exert anti-inflammatory effects in the gut to prevent COVID-19 complications	Medicals	3.44	1.000	2.083	0.040	S																																																															
		Nutritionists	3.00	0.921				2.	Amino acids (such as arginine and glutamine) in walnuts, peanuts, almonds and cashew nuts can facilitate immunity	Medicals	3.44	1.118	-0.425	0.672	NS	Nutritionists	3.53	0.706	3.	Omega-3 fatty acids (in fish and fish oil) can help reduce	Medicals	2.82	0.928	-2.711	0.008	S	Nutritionists	3.35	0.849	4.	Limiting the consumption of high glycemic carbohydrates (i.e., highly processed carbohydrate foods) such as refined wheat, white rice, breakfast cereals, cakes, watermelon, pineapple, and dried fruits and soon been reported to be related to the proper immune system functioning	Medicals	3.18	1.020	-0.143	0.887	NS	Nutritionists	3.21	0.914	5.	Food sources of dietary fibre such as fruits, vegetables, nuts and seeds, and potatoes with peels are of importance in metabolic functions.	Medicals	3.75	0.786	-1.122	0.265	NS	Nutritionists	3.91	0.288	6.	Mineral elements (such as zinc and selenium) obtained from food sources such as meats, fish, cereals, dairy products, fruits, vegetables, and nuts are important in increasing resistance against infections.	Medicals	3.65	0.876	-1.489	0.140	NS	Nutritionists	3.88	0.327	Grand		Medicals	20.28	3.904	-0.818	0.415	NS
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nN = Number of Nutritionists
COP = Cut-Off-Point
 \bar{x} = Mean Value of Responses
NS = Not Significant
t = Calculated t-value

Table 3 shows the mean responses of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the specific nutrition-based measures in the management of the COVID-19 Pandemic. The mean values of the responses ranged from 2.82 to 3.91 which is greater than the cut-off point of 2.50. This means both sets of respondents agreed that the specific dietary habit necessary for managing COVID-19 infection include the consumption of food sources of dietary fibre, mineral elements (such as zinc and selenium), amino acids (arginine and glutamine), high biological value proteins, lipids like the Omega -3 fatty acids, and limiting the consumption of high glycemic carbohydrates. The standard deviations of the responses range from 0.288 to 1.118 indicating that the responses are slightly scattered around the mean. However, the t-test analysis revealed that the responses of the medical practitioners and nutritionists are not significantly different on the foregoing points, except for their perspectives on the roles played by high biological value proteins and lipids in COVID-19 Management. On a cumulative ground, there is no significant difference between the perspectives of medical practitioners and nutritionists on the specific nutrition-based measures in the management of the COVID-19 Pandemic.

VII. DISCUSSION

The result of the study revealed that coronavirus has consequences such as interstitial pneumonia and respiratory distress syndrome, breakdown of the immune system, acute inflammation of the respiratory tract, multi-organ failure upon advancement of the disease, pulmonary tissue damage, stigmatization of patients, damage in the blood vessels, and mortality. The studies carried out by Ding *et al.* (2020), Guan *et al.* (2020), Zangrillo *et al.* (2020) and Zhou *et al.* (2020) confirmed these findings. Furthermore, Maguire and Stone (2021), while reviewing the alliance between nurses and dietitians, discovered that more cases of advanced diseases are associated with COVID-19, and that the greater risk is that of malnutrition which then became increasingly difficult to manage by conventional means.

It was equally discovered that the general role of good nutrition in COVID-19 management includes immune boosting, increase in resistance against infections, prevention of damage to the blood vessels, control of metabolic functions and exertion of anti-inflammatory effects in the gut to prevent COVID-19 complications. Also, the specific dietary habit

necessary for managing COVID-19 infection includes the consumption of food sources of dietary fibre, mineral elements (such as zinc and selenium), amino acids (arginine and glutamine, high biological value proteins, lipids like the Omega-3 fatty acids, and limiting the consumption of high glycemic carbohydrates. Good dietary habits can help in immune boosting, exert anti-inflammatory effects in the gut to prevent COVID-19 complications, increase resistance against infections, control metabolic functions, and prevent damage to the blood vessels. This is supported by the report of Iddir *et al.* (2020), Monnier *et al.* (2006) and Zabetakis *et al.* (2020). This is in line with the position of Maguire and Stone (2021) that the standard care of COVID-19 patients (especially for those living with cancer) included routine monitoring of their nutrition, dissemination of receive targeted nutrition information, and administration of therapeutic diets. In other words, the comprehensive nutritional intervention was helpful in optimising outcomes for this highly vulnerable patient group.

However, the perspectives of medicals and nutritionists are significantly different on the general role of nutrition in the management of COVID-19, while their perspectives on the specific roles are not significantly different. Maguire and Stone (2021) explained that nurses and dietitians collaborated to provide nutritional care for COVID-19 patients, particularly those living with cancer. The first point of contact for the patients was the nurses, who liaised between patients and their respective family members during admission. The family members furnished the nurses with information such as the usual feeding habits and practices of the patients, their food allergies and preferences, and necessary home nutrition histories. This information is then used by the dietitians to recommend and deliver appropriate food services and nutritional care, as well as to carry out a comprehensive nutritional assessment of the patients.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that COVID-19 is a pandemic that has come to stay and whose effect can never be forgotten in the history of the whole world. Apart from the medications given to COVID-19 patients and the advocacy for proper hygiene, the consumption of an adequate, nutrient-dense diet can aid the management of COVID-19 before and after the infection as it will boost individuals' immune systems, thus reducing the impact of the infection on infected individuals.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The public should be made aware of the positive implications of good dietary habits on the management of the COVID-19 pandemic through newsletters and other print channels, personal contacts, billboards, social media, community and town hall meetings, sensitization on market days, and Mass media such as radio, television, internet sites.
2. Further research studies should be carried out on the effect of the coronavirus on various age groups and the nutritional requirement to manage the effects of the disease on them.
3. Government should be up and doing by assisting in the cultivation of food sources of the nutrients needed by the populace during the crisis caused by the pandemic.

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